

Technical Note: Clarification on the Acoustic Voice Quality Index Version Used in Zainae et al. (2022)

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Abstract

The Acoustic Voice Quality Index (AVQI) is a widely used multiparametric tool for objectively assessing voice quality. In our previously published 2022 study, we aimed to validate AVQI versions 2.06 and 3.01 for the Persian-speaking population. However, a subsequent review of our scripts and analysis files revealed that AVQI version 2.03, not 2.06, was used throughout the study. This technical report clarifies the discrepancy by detailing the differences between AVQI v2.03 and v2.06, including their regression formulas and acoustic parameters. Although this correction adjusts the reported version, the actual computations and results remain unaffected, as the analysis was consistently based on AVQI v2.03 as well as v3.01. This clarification does not impact the study's findings or conclusions but ensures accuracy and transparency for future applications, replications, and comparisons.

Keywords: AVQI; Acoustic Voice Quality Index; Dysphonia; Farsi; Persian; Voice Disorders.

I. Background

Voice plays a fundamental role in communication, and its effectiveness depends on the healthy function of the vocal folds. Abnormalities of the vocal folds can result in voice disorders (VDs), which are characterized by deviations in pitch, loudness, or quality and can adversely affect social, occupational, physical, and emotional well-being [1], [2]. VDs are relatively common, affecting approximately 17% of the popula-

tion at some point in life [3], with higher prevalence among voice-dependent professionals such as teachers, singers, therapists, etc. [4]–[6]. Accurate assessment and timely diagnosis of VDs are essential for effective management in such populations [7]–[9]. Among the objective tools developed for this purpose, the Acoustic Voice Quality Index (AVQI) has gained wide clinical and research utility [10]–[13]. In our 2022 study, we examined the validity of AVQI versions 2.03 and 3.01 for Persian-speaking individuals. However, a discrepancy was later identified between the AVQI version reported and the one actually used, prompting the need for clarification.

In our 2022 article titled “The Acoustic Voice Quality Index, Version 2.06 and 3.01, for the Persian-Speaking Population,” published in the *Journal of Communication Disorders*, we aimed to validate the clinical utility of AVQI versions 2.03 and 3.01 for Persian-speaking individuals [14]. The Ethics Committee of Mashhad University of Medical Sciences approved the study (No. IR.MUMS.REC.1398.286). Informed consent was given by all the participants for the use of their data for this study. The study involved 180 native Persian speakers from Mashhad, Iran, including both normophonic individuals and those with dysphonia from various etiologies. Acoustic analyses were conducted using Praat scripts, and auditory-perceptual evaluations were performed by five experienced speech-language pathologists using the GRBAS Grade scale and a visual analog scale. The results demonstrated high intra- and inter-rater reliability, strong concurrent validity, and excellent diagnostic accuracy for both AVQI versions. Specifically, version 2.03 yielded thresholds of 3.47 and 4.04

based on the average Grade and visual analog scale scores, respectively, while version 3.01 yielded optimal thresholds of 3.03 and 3.07 based on the same scales.

II. Clarification

A recent review of our project files and analysis scripts revealed that AVQI version 2.03, not version 2.06 as reported in the manuscript, was used throughout the study. This unintentional discrepancy was not identified during manuscript preparation or peer review and was inadvertently missed by both the authors and the reviewers. Clarifying this point is important, as AVQI version 2.03 and version 2.06 are based on different regression models.

AVQI version 2.03 was originally developed by Maryn et al. in 2010 using a regression formula that included six acoustic predictors. The final score was scaled by multiplying the output by 2.571 to produce values on a scale from zero to ten (see Equation (Maryn et al. (2010))) [15]. In that study, the value for Smoothed Cepstral Peak Prominence was extracted using the SpeechTool software, since that measure was not yet available in Praat. The other five acoustic predictors were calculated using Praat.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AVQI}_{v2.03} = & (3.295 - (0.111 \times \text{CPPS}) - (0.073 \times \text{HNR}) \\ & - (0.213 \times \text{ShimL}) + (2.789 \times \text{SLdB}) \\ & - (0.032 \times \text{Slope}) + (0.077 \times \text{Tilt})) \\ & \times 2.571 \end{aligned}$$

(Maryn et al. (2010))

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AVQI}_{v2.03} = & ((3.295 - (0.111 \times \text{CPPS}) - (0.073 \times \text{HNR}) \\ & - (0.213 \times \text{ShimL}) + (2.789 \times \text{SLdB}) \\ & - (0.032 \times \text{Slope}) + (0.077 \times \text{Tilt})) \\ & \times 2.208) + 1.797 \end{aligned}$$

(Pommée (2018))

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AVQI}_{v2.06} = & 9.072 - (0.245 \times \text{CPPS}) - (0.161 \times \text{HNR}) \\ & - (0.470 \times \text{ShimL}) + (6.158 \times \text{SLdB}) \\ & - (0.071 \times \text{Slope}) - (0.170 \times \text{Tilt}) \end{aligned}$$

(Maryn and Weenink (2015))

In 2015, Maryn and Weenink introduced an updated implementation of the AVQI procedure, often referred to as the AVQI beta version [16]. This version replaced the original SpeechTool-based measure with the newly implemented Smoothed Cepstral Peak Prominence available within Praat. A new regression model was computed using only measures extracted from Praat. This update made it possible to carry out the full analysis in one script, increasing the clinical feasibility of the AVQI protocol. Although this updated formula used different coefficients than the original version 2.03, it was not immediately assigned a consistent version label. Over time, it came to be referenced in the literature as AVQI version 02.02, as reported by Kankare et al. in 2019 [17], or as version 2.06, as cited by Yeşilli Puzella et al. in 2022 [18],

despite the regression equation being unchanged (see Equation (Maryn and Weenink (2015))).

In a later application, Pommée in 2018 validated AVQI version 2.03 for use with native French speakers. He applied the same six acoustic predictors but modified the scaling approach. The regression output was multiplied by 2.208 and then increased by 1.797 to generate the final AVQI score (see Equation (Pommée (2018))) [19]. In this implementation, all six acoustic parameters were extracted using Praat, including Smoothed Cepstral Peak Prominence, which had become available in later versions of the software. Pommée noted that the values for Smoothed Cepstral Peak Prominence obtained in Praat closely matched those from SpeechTool, which supported the use of a single-platform solution.

Although both versions are referred to as AVQI version 2.03 (see Equation (Maryn et al. (2010)) and (Pommée (2018))), the difference in scaling reflects an adaptation to better align scores with perceptual judgments and diagnostic thresholds in a specific population. In our study, we used the AVQI version 2.03 formula as implemented by Pommée.

III. Conclusion

Given these differences, we clarify that AVQI version 2.03, not 2.06, was used in our study. All analyses and reported results remain valid, as computations were correctly based on AVQI v2.03 and v3.01 from the outset. This correction does not affect the scientific conclusions or validity of our findings. Nevertheless, we recommend caution when comparing our thresholds with studies based on v2.06. Future cross-study comparisons should account for the AVQI version difference in the future to ensure methodological consistency.

IV. Funding

No external funding was received for this pilot study.

V. Conflict of interest

The authors confirm that this technical note was prepared without any commercial or financial affiliations that could be perceived as potential conflicts of interest.

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